

Illegal Gold Mining Activities on Water and Land Resources Assessment and its Impacts on Livelihoods

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ABSTRACT

Gold mining activities has been in existence over several years because of its value and income generating power. For this reason the natural resources is exploited both legally and through illegal means. The illegal gold mining means is what is called Galamsey in Ghana. By this process, gold is exploited using illegal strategies and process to access and mine the natural resource. This results in the destruction of natural resources such as lands, forest reserves, water bodies and farmlands. This research hence purposed to investigate and justify this cause as illegal gold mining activities has become rampant in Nsutam community in the Eastern Region of Ghana. It is established that illegal gold mining activities has destroyed lands, forest reserves, farmlands. River Birim which used to serve about 80% of the indigenou, is now polluted, turbid and contaminated to a higher degree hence of no interest to anyone. Research findings indicates that natural channels of the rivers is at times destroyed during gold mining by these illegal gold mining operators. The destruction of forest reserves and destruction of natural channels of rivers is leading to reduced evapotranspiration and evaporation respectively. This is impacting the hydrological cycle negatively and may lead to future repercussions. Despite the negative impacts of illegal gold mining activities within the study area, it's impacting positively on livelihoods. It is generating income into individual pockets to support families and addressing unemployment problems among the youth.

Keywords: *land, water, forest, gold, mining, illegal, livelihood, resources, galamsey, destruction, impacts, enrichment.*

1 INTRODUCTION

An illegal activity is any unacceptable activity which impacts negatively on natural resources in a community and not endorsed by a governing or regulatory body within a society or country. There are all kinds of illegal activities in the Nsutam

Community in the Eastern Region of Ghana of which illegal gold mining activities (galamsey) is the main one impacting negatively on water and land resources. Ghana is a rich country in natural resources (first gold producer in Africa and sixth in the world) with tons of gold reserves buried underground which requires exploitation, mining, usage and export. Gold mining business has become a boom in Ghana due to man's quest for riches and greatness in life. Ghanaians intentions towards natural resources is very bad as most of them are over exploited. Once they see or discover the resources, they don't seek the technical knowledge, way of exploitation, usage and maintenance. They just wants to make use and that's all, and this is exactly what has happened to all surface water bodies and lands in Ghana. The Ghanaian economy has been supported by gold mining operations over the decades and still keeping the economy on course even though politicians are misusing public funds. Nsutam community was discovered with neighboring towns; Nsuapemso, Asiakwa and Osino as gold mining towns years ago. Currently, all kinds of gold mining activities are being embarked in the community; both legally and illegally. The legal gold mining

operations are from companies with state license to operate gold mines and mine gold for locals use and export. With such companies, they make use of standard operating procedures in the gold mining business. Which implies that, they use methodologies which protects natural resources like lands and water bodies whiles mining the real gold. The illegal mining groups are the once incorporating non-standardized ways of gold mining; in this case destroying cocoa farms, farmlands, lands and natural resources.

Large land areas have been degraded depleting them of rich nutrients hence not supporting plant growth. Illegal gold mining companies have dug several kilometers and feet's underground to explore the natural resources and hence resulting in degraded lands. In Ghana, once a community is identified as a one with gold reserves, land owners are ready to sell and release lands for the exploitation of the resource resulting in its overexploitation. Farmers sell lands having cocoa farms, coconut plantations, cassava farms and oil palm plantations. Such crops and plantation on the farmlands helps in the enrichment of the soil for now and future crop productions. By the end of an illegal gold mining activity, the lands and soil are devoid of nutrients and hence unwilling to support plant production. The overexploitation of the land resource has left vast lands without nutrients and unsupportive towards crop production. Such illegal miners do not have any

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reclamation strategies in place to recoup the degradable lands for the future. In the past, Ghana was identified as one of the best cocoa producing countries in the world but not the case today due to illegal gold mining. Now, cocoa farms are sold by farmers to access lands to boost the gold mining business in Ghana. And this is resulting in the destruction and degradation of land resources in Ghana. This gold mining business will continue in Ghana due to ones enrichment after exploitation and the resultant degradation of lands because of illegalities in the process of assessment of the resource. It therefore becomes a requirement to have standard operating procedures to access for the development of the economy and enrichment of individuals in life.

Water resources are also destroyed during the illegal mining of the gold resource in Nsutam. River Birim and Supong are the two river bodies in the community and have been destroyed due to illegal gold mining in the community. The aesthetics and beauty of the river body is lost and hence not supporting daily life activities such as drinking, bathing, cooking, watering of plants on farmlands due to high turbidity. Some areas of the natural channels of the river body have been destroyed by these illegal gold miners.

2 Review of related works on gold mining

2.1 Mining in Ghana and Africa

Years ago, water bodies in Nsutam such as Supong and River Birim were in the pure, fine clean states with little sediments acceptable for washing, drinking, cooking and bathing. The rivers were used for all kinds of activities including stated above but can't be said of today due to illegal gold mining activities. Big gold mining companies like Ashanti Goldfields (Obuasi) Limited situated 160km northeast of Accra has been a legal gold mining company in Ghana over the years. The Obuasi mine has been in operation for the past 110 years and can be described as the single industrial hub of the Ghanaian economy. It has produced in excess of 30 million ounces of gold since its inception and accounts for over 60% of the total national gold production. Its inventory of global resources is estimated in the neighborhood of 80.8 million tons at 8.1 g/t (Gyapong & Amanor, 2003). Such mining companies employ good land management and water resources management (WRM) procedures protecting stool lands and water bodies. The mine has undergone extensive expansion and modernization in the last two decades resulting in the development of extensive open pit mines and increased underground mining operations boosted by the development of a mosaic of new shafts (Akabzaa, 2009). There has also been modernization of the processing technology used in the mine, with the introduction of hydrometallurgy

and bio-oxidation technologies and gradual phase-out of pyrometallurgical processing up to 2000, in a move to reduce environmental pollution on lands and water resources. The area also has a long history of native mining. Artisanal mining has been recorded in the area as early as 1471 (Kesse, 1985). Mining is required to obtain any non-renewable resource that can't be grown or created artificially in a factory or laboratory (Iminco, 2017). Africa is well endowed with mineral resources. It harbors the world's largest mineral reserves of platinum, gold, diamonds, chromite, manganese, and vanadium. However, most of these minerals are exported as ores, concentrates or metals without significant downstream processing to add value. This has led to the persistent belief that the untapped mineral potential can act as a springboard for Africa's industrialization (UNECA, 2009). However, mining activities affect the rate of contamination of water resources due to their physical degrading nature, as well as use of chemicals and other harmful substances (Adjei, 2012). There is a very long history of mining in Ghana. In particular, there is evidence of gold mining and a gold trade with North Africa going back to the middle ages. Thus, Ghana's mining production is largely driven by gold, contributing more than 95 per cent of the country's total mineral revenue (Ghana Chamber of Mines, 2015). The other commercially exploited minerals in Ghana include manganese, bauxite and diamonds. Besides, the country is also endowed with many more under-exploited deposits of iron

ore, limestone, columbite-tantalite, feldspar, quartz and salt (Ghana Chamber of Mines, 2006).

2.2 Gold mining and impacts on water resources

Gold mining in Nsutam is by both legal and illegal miners within the community with consequences on the precious water bodies. The use of water in mining has the potential to affect the quality of surrounding surface water and groundwater which is often cited as a major concern among stakeholders. Mining operations, whether small or large scale, often involve the use of water which impacts water resources, even in the long term after the closure of the operations of gold mines (Gardner et al., 2015).

Mining activities exposes metals that have been relatively immobile in a tightly bound subsurface causing them to leach into surface and ground waters in large quantities when the mined rocks are exposed to air and water. Metals at very low

dissolved levels and presence of such heavy metals above a certain threshold can be injurious to human health and the environment, particularly aquatic life. Since waste rock dumps are not lined, containment of contaminants from waste rock is frequently an issue (Miranda et al., 2005). Of major concern in terms of both the environment and public health are the cases of cyanide mismanagement by several gold mining firms which have led to the cyanide contamination of freshwater

resources and soils, adversely impacting local fish and wildlife populations and the health and livelihoods of rural farming and indigenous communities. The cyanide-laced water and sediment is stored in massive plastic lined tailings ponds that are supposed to hold the cyanide waste, but the ponds inevitably leak or the dams restraining them fail, allowing cyanide to pollute the water table or nearby rivers and streams (Armstrong, 2008).

2.3 Gold mining and impacts on land resources

The socioeconomic externalities of surface mining (e.g., loss of livelihoods, lower incomes, declines in food production, and higher costs of living) already severely threaten household food security in rural areas and on top of these inequities, the accelerating rate of deforestation only further exacerbates the deterioration of natural resources in the gold belt that is leading to the rising incidence of hunger (Osei-Bagyina, 2012). Large scale deforestation, soil fertility loss, and soil erosion have contributed to the very low level of agricultural productivity in general, and food agriculture in particular, “with current average yields about 40% of achievable yields” (Osei-Bagyina, 2012). This has adversely impacted rural communities by contributing to a decline in the productivity of agricultural lands (Armstrong, 2008). Arsenic (As) is widely distributed in the environment, originating either from arsenic in the soil parent material or from discharge of arsenic onto

land as a result of human activities (Chaturvedi, 2006). The effect of arsenic pollution in Ghana is mainly seen in those gold mining towns where sulphide ore is treated. For example, arsenic pollution in and around Obuasi has resulted in wilting and discoloration of leaves of both tap-rooted and fibrous-rooted plants in the area, which has had a serious adverse effect on agricultural activities particularly the production of cocoa, oil palm, cassava, plantain, cowpea and rice (Gawu, 2009). Due to withering of vegetation, soil erosion also tends to be severe in these areas (Chaturvedi, 2006). Due to the high pH of cyanide discharge from treatment plants, vegetation does not flourish in areas where these cyanide-rich tailings are located as can be seen at Obuasi (Gawu, 2009). Biomass production and yields of a variety of crops are reduced significantly at elevated arsenic concentrations and also understanding how arsenic is taken up by plants and subsequently transformed in plant tissue is therefore essential for estimating the risks posed to human and wildlife populations by arsenic contaminated soils (Chaturvedi, 2006).

3 STUDY AREA AND METHOD

3.1 Nature of the study area

This research work is embarked at Nsutam community in the Eastern Region of Ghana which has a population of about 7000 (2021 population census). The Nsutem community makes use of water in variable amounts but the most important affected in times of water crises are children and women. Most

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of the women are shop operators in front of houses or in containers involved in the selling of goods and services. Depicted in **Fig. 1** is the map of the study area. Indigenous within the community are involved in activities such as coconut business, farming, gold mining and other businesses which is making the community lively and enriching the lives of indigenous and migrants. The Nsutam community has been a farming community over ages with all kinds of hidden natural resources. The discovery of gold, exploration and its mining has given the community a new stand in Ghana as one of the gold mining communities towards national development. The indigenous are Akyems mixed with other tribes migrants which includes Akwapim, Asantes, Ewes, Ga's, Krobos, Fantes, northerners etc. All working and helping towards the development and wellbeing of the community.

Fig 1: Map of the Fanteakwa South depicting the study area

3.2 Methodology employed

The methodology employed in this research work is the illegal gold mining site visit questionnaire answering and observation method. Various illegal gold mining sites are visited by researcher to assess, evaluate and judge the illegal gold mining activities and its impacts on natural resources; water bodies, land and forest reserves. Various sites are visited to assess the impacts of illegal gold mining activities on livelihoods. Respondents gave various views and opinions on the impacts of illegal gold mining on individual lives and on the community.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

2.1 Environmental and forest reserves impacts by illegal gold mining

The aesthetic nature of every environment has positive impacts on the livelihood and happenings in a society. People are willing to live in a beautiful environment and all engineering works and designs are correctly done and blending with vegetation's and plants. The current nature of the environment of the Nsutam community has seen drastic changes as compared to the 1990s. The discovery of gold and the use of standard operating procedures by licensed gold mining companies and illegal gold mining has generated money into the pockets of both indigenous and immigrants contributing to the wellbeing of the community. Even though the environmental settings of Nsutam community cannot be

compared to communities in well-established countries like UK, Canada, China, Germany, Senegal, Dubai, USA etc, it's in the right direction when it comes to community development towards national development.

The forest settings within the community is under treat as lands are sold by chiefs and the indigenous for illegal gold mining business within the community. Forest vegetation's play major roles in nature and in any country. The southern part of Ghana has a lot of forest zones and areas and Nsutam is no exception but these are being destroyed through illegal gold mining. Considering the hydrological cycle, forest and plant vegetation's plays roles in sustaining the cycle. During a storm for instance, rainfall interception reduces soil erosion and contributes to high amount of infiltration resulting in moist soil to promote plant production. Evapotranspiration results in high amount of water evaporating into the sky to contribute to cloud formation and resultant rainfall for the continuity of the hydrological cycle. This continues seasonal rainfall in the southern part is what is maintaining the forest zones and its existence. Because of this, the forest formation and zones in the southern part cannot be compared to the northern part due to twice and once rainfall seasons within the southern and northern part respectively experienced each year. The rainfall regime within the southern part and its contribution towards plant growth and formation is helping in maintaining the moist, cool and nutrient level of the lands

to support plant growth. But this is not the case in the northern part of Ghana as most of the lands do not support plant growth and thick forest formation hence once in a year plant production. Illegal gold mining business which has become rampant in the southern part of Ghana and in Nsutam is destroying these forest reserves as can be seen on Atiwa Forest and the associated impacts on nature. Plant foliage contributes hugely into the hydrological cycle and if all plants extinct from the southern part of Ghana and Nsutam, the cycle will be broken and the resultant negative repercussions may occur. There is hence the need to protect the forest reserves by using good gold mining practices through standard operating procedures which are international standards for gold mining to access the natural resource for the benefit of mankind and Ghana.

Plate 1: Destroyed forest reserves by illegal gold mining

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2.2 Impacts of illegal gold mining on water resources

The beauty, quality and nature of most water bodies in Ghana is not appealing at all due to the impacts of illegal gold mining on surface water sources. Water has major roles to play in the existence of life on planet earth and in the formation of rainfall for the continuity of the hydrological cycle in nature. It again play roles in the extraction of gold either through standard operating procedures or illegal means. Even though, illegal gold mining activities was seen in the 1990s, in areas like Osino and environs, water was still being used although of impurities to an extent. This is not the case in the 2020s as illegal gold mining in Nsutam and its environs like Osino, Asiakwa, Ankase etc has become serious leading to the destruction of the finite good. The only sources of water within the study area and this areas was rainwater and surface water from the water bodies. And rainfall season throughout the year was twice a year hence community indigenous resorting to the surface water when in need. This is not the case today hence no or little use of surface water; river Birim, Supong, Akusu etc. The establishment of boreholes (both hand pumps ones and those abstracted upstream into polytanks for storage and distribution), sachet water, well water and treated water from government agencies such as Ghana Water Company Limited has led to about 5% of the Nsutam population making use of surface water such as river Birim and

Supong. So in this scenario, Ghana Water Company Limited (GWCL) is the main beneficiary of the surface water like Birim. But this Birim has been destroyed and contaminated due to illegal gold mining activities. The company hence uses huge amount of money when it comes to the treatment of the water abstracted from Birim due to high turbidity and contamination. This is even sold at a higher price for users and upon comparing to other sources of water available like boreholes, well water, less usage of the water from GWCL. With this analysis, the pressure and usage of water bodies within the community is at a very low rate due to destruction by illegal gold mining activities. If this is not addressed by government agencies, stakeholders and non-governmental organizations, these water bodies may die in the near future as illegal gold mining activities is destroying the natural channels of most of these water bodies. If all these surface water bodies die, there will be no source to charge groundwater, evaporate into the sky to contribute to hydrological cycle and resultant rainfall formation to support plant growth and formation of forest reserves. Illegal gold mining is on the rise in Ghana and impacting all kinds of surface water bodies in Ghana. Water bodies are linked and by that, as a river source flows from upstream to downstream, it ends up joining another water body. The destruction of natural channels and redirection of river bodies is a very bad engineering work. Upon breaking this chain of natural channel

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linkage through bad engineering work, a bigger river having its source from a smaller river will end. And the resultant impact is continual drying of both rivers. The final end product will be the extinction of the rivers and the future consequences.

The chemicals used in illegal gold mining also is affecting water bodies as it does not support daily human water usage activities like cooking, drinking, washing, watering. Field visit and investigations concludes that, some indigenous makes use of illegal gold mining waste water to meet some of these water demands in the homes as a girl was met on illegal mining site fetching water for drinking. This will result in health problems in the future upon continuous use of the waste water. In times past, most of these surface water sources were used in irrigation on farmlands and nursing of seedlings but this is not the case today as the water is too turbid and contaminated to a higher degree to serve this purpose. Because of this most watering, nursing, irrigation are done using water from boreholes. There is therefore the need to address the issue of illegal gold mining activities in Nsutam and in Ghana to protect water bodies and water resources to address the problems discussed above to avoid future eventualities.

Plate 2: Turbid and contaminated river Birim by illegal gold miners

2.3 impacts of illegal gold mining on land resources

Land resources plays all kinds of roles in the development of every country whether rich in nutrients or devoid of nutrients. Most natural resources such as gold, bauxite, manganese, oil, water etc are all buried underground. To access for national development and human consumption, it requires feasibility studies, investigation, exploration, mining and refinement into consumable and usable products. On the surface of lands are plants, forest reserves, natural and artificial channels of water, buildings and structures to support daily activities, all engineering works and so on. Hence land being an important natural resource which one cannot do away with. So is Nsutam the study area blessed with this natural resources and buried underground is the natural resource, gold

requiring investigation, exploration, mining and refinement into products for enrichment and helping the wellbeing of mankind. But due to man's quest for easy and early riches in life, is overexploiting the gold resulting in the destruction of lands. Vast amount of lands in the study area, its environs and Ghana are being destroyed due to illegal gold mining business in Ghana. Illegal gold mining activities is depleting lands of nutrients, water and natural organisms which help enrich the soil for crop production. Ghana as a country is blessed with good rainfall patterns which is always helping reclaim the lands after leaving it for several years of not altering the land through illegal gold mining. Farming activities always become a problem in areas where these illegal gold mining activities is rampant. There is a connection between rich lands, forest reserves, surface water, underground water, oceans or seas and rainfall. Nations or land surface areas with bad rainfall regime and patterns are areas where this connection does not exist. In such areas, there is a break in the hydrological cycle hence no good rainfall patterns resulting in lands not good in nutrients to support all kinds of activities. Illegal gold mining activities in the study area and in Ghana which has become severe and still ongoing may in the future result in a break in the hydrological cycle if care is not taking. If this happens, southern lands will be like lands in the northern part which do not support plant production all season. Research findings indicates that, illegal gold mining lands are left bare with

no plating activity occurring over the land for several years. There is no reclamation procedures and strategies to claim the lands back to its natural states full of nutrients to support plant production and other activities. State institutions in charge of lands in all illegal gold mining sites in Ghana and worldwide needs to look into some of the issues raised and addressed above to protect state and country lands from illegal gold mining. If not and there is a break in the natural cause resulting in good rainfall regimes, desertification will take place. A change or break in the hydrological cycle due to illegal activities like gold mining at Nsutam results in climate changes over the region, future consequences and associated issues.

Plate 3: Destroyed land resources due to illegal gold mining at Nsutam

24. Effects of illegal gold mining activities on livelihood at Nsutam

Before the inception and surging of gold mining activities within the Nsutam

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community, it was only known as a stopover point for vehicles from Accra to Kumasi and vice versa. Passengers then take it as an opportunity to attend to all kinds of issues such as something to eat for strength and energy for the rest of the journey to their destinations. The community became a vibrant community will all kinds of migration both locally and internationally into the community to start gold exploration and mining. This resulted in both legal and illegal gold mining which has impacted Nsutam both positively and negatively. The negative impacts is on water resources, land resources, forest reserves as discussed above. The positive impacts can be justified with the new building and engineering settings of the community as compared to the 1990s. The gold mining business has opened the community for other business operations such as manufacturers of roofing sheets and housing roofing; construction of a university; petty trading businesses; onion trading etc. It can now be confirmed as a 24 hours business operation community because of the gold mining business. There is also increase in the population of the community as there is daily migration by people into the community in search of jobs and opportunities. This has made the community a lively one boosting community development and national development. Farming activities by the indigenous and migrants is also an activity that is also supporting the livelihood of the community. Even though most of the lands have been sold to miners to boost the

illegal gold mining activities, subsistence farming still continues within the community to support families. The destruction of water bodies is negatively affecting livelihoods as it used to be previously. Good quality river Birim in times past was used to serve recreational purposes such as for bathing and fishing. The establishment of paradise resort in addition to Linda Dor is meeting recreational purposes on special occasions. This is impacting positively as its generating income for owners whiles serving as entertainment joints for people and community during special days.

5 CONCLUSIONS

While the mined natural resources of a country generates income to boost economic growth and development, the community within which such a resource exist also benefits. Royalties are paid by all gold mining companies to chiefs and owners of communities and so is Nsutam community. This motivates land owners and chiefs to sell lands for gold exploration and mining. This has resulted and increased the illegal gold mining business in Ghana and in Nsutam community. The illegal gold mining operations within Nsutam community has impacted negatively and destroyed farmlands, forest reserves, polluted and contaminated water bodies such as river Birim and Spong, and causing nuisance in the environment. The natural aesthetic beauty of the environment has been destroyed due to the quest for riches in life through illegal gold mining within Nsutam

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community. Even though illegal gold mining activities have negative impacts on water resources, land resources and forest reserves in the study area, it has an aspect of positive importance offer. It has given employment and a sense of direction to unemployed youth, generated money into individual pockets and impacted positively on livelihoods. This youths are able to build houses and generated thousands of cedis into pockets to support families. It therefore deems important for the government and agencies to collaborate and organize this illegal mining business to meet international standards. In doing so, income from gold mining activities will be obtained while protecting and conserving natural resources; lands, forest reserves, water bodies, farmlands, plant foliage and state resources.

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